

ISic1308

Funerary inscription for Kornelios Agathemeros

Language

Ancient Greek with Latin numerals

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tablet

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Found in the mid-eighteenth century during foundation works for the Collegio di Maria (founded in 1752), outside the Porta

Stesicorea (Porta di Aci), on the
eastern side of Piazza Stesicoro. Found with the inscription
no.27, set up by the same
man.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 287

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 19.5 cm

Width 29 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 12-25 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. □ Θ(εοῖς) Κ(αταχθονίοις) □
2. Κορνήλιος · Ἄγα
3. θήμερος · ἔζη ·
4. σεν ἔτη · XXXVIII
5. Εὐφροσύνη · ἰδίῳ συν
6. βίῳ μνήμης χάριν

Apparatus

text from photograph

Translation (en)

To the gods of the underworld. Kornelios Agathemerios lived 38 years.
Eufrosyne (set this up) as a
 memorial for her own partner in life.

Translation (it)

Agli dèi del mondo sotterraneo. Kornelios Agathemerios ha vissuto 38 anni.
Eufrosia (lo pose) a
 ricordo del proprio compagno di vita.

Commentary

This epitaph was found together with ISic1314 (inv. no.272), which was apparently erected by the same man as is commemorated in this text (although it is also possible that they are father and son). The implication is that Eufrosyne was his second wife, who outlived him. The use of Latin numerals in the middle of the Greek text is a clear indication of the co-existence of the two languages in Catania at this date and the 'interference' between them (just as the name Cornelius Agathemerios combines Latin and Greek names also).

Digital identifiers:

TM 492913

EDCS 39101678

PHI 140800

PHI 316213

Bibliography

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Photo by students of Liceo M.M. Lazzaro, Catania